

Topological Data Analysis and Persistence Theory Applications to Heart Arrhythmia

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Abstract

There are over 550 million people worldwide who suffer from heart disease and related conditions. Thus, effective heart disease detection is a central discovery-driven medical problem that will help doctors make more informed decisions. Although machine learning, and specifically deep learning, has made substantial progress on developing detection algorithms, these models often become unreliable when data is excessively noisy or has minor perturbations. In recent years, a statistical analysis technique that has gradually gained popularity is that of topological data analysis, where tools from algebraic topology are applied in a statistical setting. This technique is less sensitive to noise than standard machine learning. We study uses of topological data analysis and a sub-topic known as persistence theory to analyze ECG data of patients suffering from a heart condition known as arrhythmia, a form of abnormal cardiac beating. We use topological properties obtained from our analysis to differentiate between arrhythmia patients and healthy controls and use these properties to provide an alternative arrhythmia detection algorithm from the existing literature.

Key Words: dimensionality reduction, time delay embedding, persistent homology, topological data analysis, filtration

1. Introduction

Big data has become an increasingly common term. However, often, this data is large, complex, and full of noise. To make a valid conclusion from big data, we must have a way to extract certain features of the data without losing others. Topological Data Analysis, or TDA for short, is a novel new method to address this challenge. TDA is based on the idea that data has shape; this shape can be exploited via topological and geometrical tools. These can provide a powerful way to obtain useful qualitative information about the data. In recent years, TDA has provided mathematical and statistical methods for analyzing complex data, and many software libraries have become available for this type of analysis, including the GUDHI library in Python, R studio, and Giotto.

In this context, data refers to a collection of points along a time series. The horizontal axis of the variable will be the time coordinate, while the vertical coordinate of the point is the metric we are studying. When we have a collection of these data points with a notion of distance that satisfies the criteria for a metric space, we refer to this collection as a point cloud.

In this paper, we will use the technique of persistent homology to count many topological features of the time series embedding, including connected components, as well as other higher dimensional topological properties, such as holes, tunnels, and voids. In this paper, we will study the 0-dimensional topological structures of the time series embeddings of patients suffering from Ventricular Tachycardia and those of healthy controls. It is good practice to analyze the 0-dimensional homology of data rather than 1-dimensional homology and higher dimensional homologies because while higher dimensional homologies can occasionally yield interesting results that cannot be seen from lower dimensional homologies, it is much more difficult to do, and the results are much harder to interpret. It is still not agreed upon how to interpret the Betti sequences of higher dimensional homologies, and the topological features identified from a higher dimensional analysis can vary greatly from a change in the time series embedding dimension or the time delay. As a result, the conclusions drawn from higher dimensional analysis are often questionable.

Throughout this paper, 0-dimensional topological features are referring to the connected parts between the sublevel subsets within the time series embedding. Subsequent to a piecewise linear interpolation of this time series embedding, we can begin to analyze the topological features of this 3-dimensional point cloud. As the time series embedding is thickened (aka. the sublevel subsets of the embedding increase) and previously disjoint connected components merge, and new connected parts are formed, the number of connected components either increases or decreases. When a new connected component is added, we refer to this as the birth of that topological feature. Similarly, when two connect components merge and one of the components is lost, we denote this as an instance of the death of a connected component. To depict all of these instances of birth and death as the sublevel subsets increase, we use a depiction known as a persistence diagram. An alternative representation is a persistence barcode, which encodes the same information. In this paper, we will mainly use persistence diagrams, as this is the most standard way to depict birth and death times in the current topological literature.

The topic of analyzing the heart rate variability (HRV) from ECG/EKG data has been an important and well-studied area, and in this paper, we continue to build on this research as we introduce and examine the efficacy of a novel method of detecting Ventricular Tachycardia using persistent homology on the time series generated by ECG data, with a unique application of a time series delay. General uses of methods from topological data analysis have shown promise in numerous other recent studies. The analysis of the topology of data has been applied to crack propagation in the field of fracture mechanics, the spread of the COVID-19 epidemic in the United States, the spread of the Zika Virus in Brazil, as well as the detection of general Arrhythmia from time series data. However, previous work has been unable to detect specific properties of Arrhythmia. Arrhythmia is a broad disease, with numerous different types, and there are two properties of Arrhythmia that are crucial for a proper diagnosis: the location of the Arrhythmia as well as the relative rate of the ECG signal (whether it is going faster or slower than normal). In this paper, we study Ventricular Tachycardia, the specific form of Arrhythmia that originates in the ventricles (the lower chamber of the heart) and whose rate is faster than normal. This is important as the origin of the Arrhythmia and the classification of its abnormalities are key to properly treating the patient and protecting them from the possible consequences of leaving Ventricular Tachycardia untreated, which include cardiac arrest, a heart attack, or in severe cases, sudden death. To ensure that we properly extract topological features of the time series embedding, we will use short segments of the recordings of ECG data from the MIT Physionet Database.

We begin by stating the formal definitions of metric spaces, simplicial complexes, Betti numbers, and persistence/persistent homology, with a specific focus on the Cech and Vietoris Rips complexes. The Vietoris Rips complex is the key tool we will use for topological data analysis throughout this paper. Next, we provide details about the data set that we will be doing our analysis on, followed by a discussion of all of the operations that we will apply to the raw data with images of the resulting point clouds and diagrams displaying the relevant topological information. We then include a copy of all of the code used in the topological data analysis for completeness and describe our results and conclusions.

2. Background and Methods

In this section, we rigorously define the required mathematical tools and the actual mathematical tools that are being utilized under all the code and topological data analysis algorithms. Many definitions and notations utilized will be consistent with Edelsbrunner and Harer's work.

2.1 Metric Spaces

First, we define what a metric space is. This structure will be how we interpret a time series of ECG data.

Definition 2.1 (Metric Space): A metric space consists of a set of points M and a distance function $d : M \times M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$. This function d must satisfy a set of three criteria, which are as follows:

- (i) d is symmetric ($\forall a, b \in M, d(a, b) = d(b, a)$)
- (ii) $\forall a, b \in M, d(a, b) \geq 0$, with equality if and only if $a = b$. (in other words, d is positive definite)
- (iii) d satisfies the triangle inequality ($\forall a, b, c \in M, d(a, b) \leq d(a, c) + d(c, b)$)

Metric spaces are important because they are a type of topological space, and thus we can use our topological tools on them. In this paper, the metric space will be a set of points in 2D space (a point cloud), with the distance metric being 2D Euclidean distance.

2.2 Simplicial Complexes

The main tool for showing the topology behind the complex structures of an object is to use a fundamental object known as a *simplicial complex*. In this subsection, we define a simplicial complex, and in a later subsection we will introduce the specific complexes that we use in this paper, namely the Cech complex and the Vietoris-Rips complex, which is just a specific case of the Cech complex.

The definition of a *simplex* is a generalized "triangle" of arbitrary dimension. If we denote a subset of the vertices of a point cloud as $\{p_i\}_{i=0}^q$, where $\{p_i\}_{i=0}^q \in \mathbb{R}^n$, for a certain number of dimensions n , with q and n being positive integers with the number of points in point cloud not exceeding the number of dimensions of the topological space, then we define the notion of a q -simplex as the smallest region that contains the entire set $\{p_i\}_{i=0}^q$, or in other words, the convex hull of all the points. For the sake of this paper,

assume that $\{p_i\}_{i=0}^q$ is a set of affinely independent points. Thus, using this definition, we can see that the vertices within the topological space are 0 simplices (0-dimensional homological structures), edges between vertices are 1 simplices (1-dimensional homological structures), “triangles” (three edges with the space in between them) are 2 simplices (2-dimensional homological structures), and “tetrahedra” (a figure with four triangles as faces and the space in between them) are 3 simplices (3-dimensional homological structures). We can continue into higher dimensions, where each n simplex can be defined inductively based on lower dimensional simplices.

Let γ denote the q simplex of the set $\{p_i\}_{i=0}^q$. Vice versa, we can define $V(\gamma) = \{p_i\}_{i=0}^q$. As stated previously, any n simplex can be constructed from k dimensional simplices, where $k < n$. We now study the relationship between simplices which have different dimensions. Note that $\forall x \subseteq V(\gamma)$, we have that x is affinely independent, which follows from the way we have defined $\{p_i\}_{i=0}^q$, and thus the convex hull of all the points in the set x form a $|x|$ simplex. x in this context is known as a *face* of the original q simplex γ , or, more specifically, a $|x|$ face.

A simplicial complex of dimension of \mathbb{R}^n is then just the group of these (finite) simplices γ in \mathbb{R}^n such that $\forall \gamma$ which are in the simplicial complex, any face of γ is also a simplex in the simplicial complex, and for any pair of simplices in the simplicial complex, the intersection of the simplices is a face of both of the original simplices, and so their intersection is also in the original simplicial complex. To put this in a notational form:

Definition 2.2 (Simplicial Complex): A simplicial complex S in \mathbb{R}^n (of dimension n) is a group of (finite) n dimensional simplices $\{\gamma\}$ such that:

- (i) $\forall \gamma_i \in S, \forall f$ such that f is a face of $\gamma_i, f \in S$.
- (ii) $\forall \gamma_i, \gamma_j \in S$, the intersection of the two simplices γ_i and γ_j is a face of both γ_i and γ_j .

Note that as a consequence of (i), it also follows that the intersection of the two simplices is also a simplex of S .

2.3 Betti Numbers

Betti numbers are used to encode data about all the topological features of a point cloud, including connected components as well as higher dimensional structures such as holes, tunnels, voids, etc. Betti numbers form the fundamental building blocks of persistent homology and are a cornerstone in topological data analysis, so understanding of them is crucial.

As stated before, when studying simplicial complexes, we are really analyzing the relationship between simplexes of different dimensions. *Betti numbers* are the conventional way of encoding this information. In general, the d th Betti number represents the number of d dimensional holes that an object has. Thus, the 0th dimensional Betti number, denoted β_0 , counts the number of connected components, the 1th dimensional Betti number, denoted β_1 counts the number of tunnels, the 2nd dimensional Betti number, denoted β_2 , counts the number of voids, and so on. The Betti number is a significant invariant in topology and can be used to differentiate between different topological spaces. Hence, we see that Betti numbers are a powerful tool to

study the holes in topological objects which have different dimensions. Throughout this paper, the topological objects we are studying will typically be simplicial complexes.

Suppose we have a set of q simplices $\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_n$, and collectively, they form a simplicial complex S .

Definition 2.3 (q -chain): Consider all operations over the integers modulo 2. Then given a sequence x_i such that all x_i are in the integers modulo 2, the sum $\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i x_i$ is known as a q chain.

We often consider the collection of q chains: this set is commonly denoted in literature as $C_q(S)$. To relate the simplicial complexes of different dimensions, we can analyze the relation between their respective chains. This relation is known as a *boundary map*.

Definition 2.4 (Boundary map): The q th *boundary map*, which we will denote as ∂_q (a common notation in the literature), maps $\partial_q: C_q(S) \rightarrow C_{q-1}(S)$, with all operations done in the integers modulo 2. When ∂_q is applied to a simplex in S , denote it $\{p_0, p_1, \dots, p_q\}$, the operator iteratively removes the i th element from the i th set in the tuple, essentially acting like a “drop out” operation. A *boundary map* is also known as a *boundary homomorphism* due to the fact that $\partial_q: C_q(S) \rightarrow C_{q-1}(S)$ can be observed to be a homomorphism between the chain groups.

One important note to make is that when using boundary maps, coefficients are typically very simple and we do not have to account for sign changes because we are in the integers modulo 2. If not, signs and coefficients for boundary map and homeomorphism expressions would likely be much more complex, with the added difficulty of having to often deal with alternating signs throughout numerous expressions. A standard example of a boundary map is one where $S = \{\{a\}, \{b\}, \{c\}, \{a,b\}, \{a,c\}, \{b,c\}, \{a,b,c\}\}$ aka. a triangle. Notice that $\partial_2\{a,b,c\} = \{a,b\} + \{b,c\} + \{a,c\}$, and is thus nontrivial. However, $\partial_1(\partial_2\{a,b,c\}) = \partial_1(\{a,b\} + \{b,c\} + \{a,c\}) = \{a\} + \{b\} + \{c\} + \{a\} + \{b\} + \{c\} = 0$, and thus, is trivial. In fact, this phenomenon holds in general as well.

Theorem 1 (Composition of two consecutive boundary maps): The composition of any two consecutive boundary homomorphisms is a trivial homomorphism.

Now that we have the composition of consecutive boundary maps is trivial, we can take a nested mapping between numerous chains, formally defined as a chain complex. Let us denote $G_q(S) := \ker(\partial_q)$ and $B_q(S) := \text{im}(\partial_{q+1})$, where \ker is the kernel of the boundary homomorphism and im is image of the homomorphism. Now we can define the q th homology.

Definition 2.6 (q th Homology): Note that all the $B_q(S) := \text{im}(\partial_{q+1})$, are subspaces of their respective $G_q(S) := \ker(\partial_q)$, and so we can define, using the standard notation in literature, $H_q(S)$ as the quotient $G_q(S) / B_q(S)$. The $H_q(S)$ quotient space is known as the q th homology.

Using all of these, we can define the Betti number as the dimension of this q th homology.

Definition 2.7 (Betti Number): Let $\beta_q(S)$ denote the q th Betti number. Then $\beta_q(S)$ is equal to the dimension of the q th homology of a simplex S , $H_q(S)$.

Some other names for $H_q(S)$ that are also standard in the literature are the q th homology group, and in this case, the q th Betti number β_q can be interpreted as the rank of H_q . With the use of Betti numbers, we are able to express our results and compute the number of q dimensional holes of an arbitrary topological object; thus, they will serve as a core building block of persistent homology, the main component and technique that forms the mathematical underpinnings of our topological data analysis pipeline.

2.4 Persistent Homology and Persistence Diagrams

Persistent homology (also known as persistence homology) is in essence an extension of normal homology. The advantage of using persistent homology as compared to homology is that persistent homology helps to get rid of the noisy data in a point cloud. To get rid of this noise in persistent homology, we apply a technique known as a *filtration*. This can be visualized as a “thickening” of the point cloud, where a sequence of simplicial complexes is generated by this filtration, each one with a larger “thickening” than the last. Through the sequence of simplicial complexes, we can observe the changes in the topological features of the point cloud and the birth and death of various holes of specified dimensions through the filtration.

Definition 2.8. (Edelsbrunner and Harer, Filtration): For an index set I , a filtration is a sequence of simplicial complexes, $\{K_t\}_{t \in I}$, satisfying

$$K_{t_1} \subseteq K_{t_2}$$

whenever $t_1 \leq t_2$.

Intuitively, the above definition should make sense. After a set of connected components are merged, they should not separate again later in the sequence of the filtration.

In the previous section, we showed how given a simplicial complex, we could find the homology group and Betti number of it. In the sequence of simplicial complexes defined from a filtration, one can observe from the previous definition that every previous simplicial complex is contained in the current one. As a result, we can think of these simplicial complexes as being “nested” within the subsequent simplicial complexes, and thus, we can observe the alterations that occur in the Betti numbers and the homology groups of the simplicial complexes in the sequence from the filtration.

To see this, $\forall i \leq j$, we can construct a homomorphism $f_p^{i,j} : H_p(K_i) \rightarrow H_p(K_j)$ for all dimensions p . The filtration can then be thought of as chain of homology groups of each of the respective simplicial complexes as follows:

$$0 = H_p(K_0) \rightarrow H_p(K_1) \rightarrow \cdots \rightarrow H_p(K_n).$$

As we move through the chain, some holes are lost while at other points, some holes are gained. We now formally define the notion of a persistent homology.

Definition 2.9. (Edelsbrunner and Harer, Persistent Homology/Persistent Homology Groups): Let $\{\mathbb{K}_i\}_{i=0}^n$ be a filtration of simplicial complexes. For $q \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ and $i, j \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$ with $i \leq j$, we define the persistent homology (group) as $H_q^{i,j} := \frac{Z_q(\mathbb{K}_i)}{B_q(\mathbb{K}_j) \cap Z_q(\mathbb{K}_i)}$. The persistent homology group consists of all the homology classes (in other words, holes) of K_i that are still alive at K_j .

Because the simplicial complexes in sequence of filtrations are nested, the q chains of these simplicial complexes are also nested, and so the denominator of the persistent homology is a valid subspace, and it is well-defined with respect to $Z_q(K_i)$.

Definition 2.10 (Edelsbrunner and Harer, Birth and Death): Let $\{K_i\}_{i=0}^n$ be a filtration of simplicial complexes and let γ be a p th hole in $H_p(K_i)$. We say that γ is *born* at K_i if $\gamma \notin H_p^{i-1,i}$. Furthermore, if γ is born at K_i then it *dies* entering K_j if it merges with another hole as we go from K_{j-1} to K_j .

We can depict the persistent Betti numbers (the ranks of the persistence groups) by constructing a point cloud in two dimensions known as a *persistence diagram*. Let $\mu_p^{i,j}$ be the number of p dimensional holes which were born at K_i in the filtration and died at K_j , then we have $\mu_p^{i,j} = (\beta_p^{i,j-1} - \beta_p^{i,j}) - (\beta_p^{i-1,j-1} - \beta_p^{i-1,j}) \forall i < j, p$. To see that this is the case, just note that the first term represents the number of holes that were born at or before K_i in the sequence and that died when entering K_j , and the second term is the number that are born at before K_{i-1} in the sequence and that died when entering K_j .

To construct the p th persistence diagram, which depicts all the birth and death times of p -dimensional holes in the structures, we construct all points (a_i, a_j) with a multiplicity of $\mu_p^{i,j}$, and we can denote this persistence diagram as $\text{Dgm}_p(f)$. If we define the *persistence* of a point to be $a_j - a_i$, then the vertical distance to the diagonal of the persistence diagram is equivalent to the value of the persistence, and as is usual convention, we add in all the points on the diagonal in the persistence diagram as well. A persistence diagram is useful because it lets us quickly compute persistent Betti numbers. To compute $\beta_p^{k,l}$, we just compute the number of points in the upper left quadrant with corner point (a_k, a_l) . Thus, by studying the persistence diagram, we are able to study the topology of the entire point cloud as a whole.

2.5 The Cech and Vietoris Rips Complexes

In this paper, the simplicial complex that we will use is the Vietoris Rips Complex and the filtration will be the Rips filtration. In order to apply the Vietoris Rips complex to a time series, we must first use Taken's embedding to embed the time series in a higher dimensional point cloud. The definitions and notation used in this section are consistent with that of the Giotto documentation.

Theorem 3. (Giotto, Taken's Embedding Theorem): Denote a time series by $\{x_t, t \in T\}$. Choose a time delay of ρ and an embedding dimension of size d . Then the time series embedding will become a set of d dimensional vectors, specifically, if we represent the time series as a function $f: A \rightarrow B$ and denote the embedding by T , then $T(f) = \{[f(t), f(t - \rho), f(t - 2\rho), \dots, f(t - (d - 1)\rho)]^T | t \in A\}$.

There is no universally agreed upon method to choosing the parameters ρ and d . In this paper, we use the concept of mutual information to determine ρ and set $d = 3$ for the ease of computation and visualization.

Theorem 4 (Giotto, Mutual information): To determine the best ρ we first calculate the maximum x_{\max} and x_{\min} values of the time series, and divide the interval $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ into a large number of bins. We let p_k be the probability that an element of the time series is in the k th bin and $p_{j,k}$ be the probability that x_i is in the j th bin while $x_{i+\rho}$ is in the k th bin.

Then the mutual information is defined as $I(\rho) = - \sum_{j=1}^{n_{\text{bins}}} \sum_{k=1}^{n_{\text{bins}}} p_{j,k}(\rho) \log \frac{p_{j,k}(\rho)}{p_j p_k}$. The first minimum of $I(\rho)$ gives the optimal time delay since there we get the most information by adding $x_{i+\rho}$.

Once we have embedded the time series into a point cloud, we construct simplices between points that are within a certain distance, where distance in this paper is defined by the Euclidean metric. For a formal definition, we have:

Definition 2.11. (Giotto, Vietoris Rip's Complex): Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\} \in \mathbb{R}^p$ be a point cloud and take some $\epsilon > 0$. The *Vietoris Rips complex* is a collection of all simplexes σ with vertices in X with diameter less than 2ϵ .

It should be intuitive that for an increasing sequence $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \dots, \epsilon_{N-1}, \epsilon_N$, the Vietoris Rips complexes construct a filtration, as if two vertices are within ϵ_i of each other, then they are obviously within ϵ_j of each for any $j > i$ because $\epsilon_j > \epsilon_i$.

3. Information on Datasets

The data that we will be using comes from the datasets ‘‘CU Ventricular Tachyarrhythmia Database’’ and ‘‘Combined measurement of ECG, Breathing and Seismocardiograms’’ available at the MIT PhysioNet database.

The dataset ‘‘CU Ventricular Tachyarrhythmia Database’’ was a dataset that was published on May 2, 2007. The dataset houses 35 ECG recordings, each of which is eight minutes long. These ECG recordings were taken from people who were undergoing episodes of highly sustained Ventricular Tachycardia. The recordings were recorded by Floyd M. Nolle from patients at the Creighton University Cardiac Center. These signals were digitized with a frequency of 250 Hz and were put through an active Bessel low-pass filter. This filter was specifically of second order. In addition, the signals were at a 12-bit resolution which were taken over a 10 V range. Each of these 35 recordings contains over 127,000 samples, which comes out to be approximately just under 9 minutes of ECG time series data.

The dataset ‘‘Combined measurement of ECG, Breathing and Seismocardiograms’’ was a dataset that was published on December 12, 2014. The dataset has a collection of ECG time series data from a set of 20 healthy volunteers. It is important to note that after the ECG sensors were connected onto the volunteers, their basal states were all recorded, determined by their ECG data for approximately 5 minutes. All the data in this dataset was recorded with a Biopac MP36 data acquisition system.

4. Application to Heart Disease Data

The purpose of this brief section is to visually illustrate an example of our topological data analysis algorithm applied to several example samples of the original time series data from the healthy control and patients suffering from Ventricular Tachycardia, Ventricular Flutter, and Ventricular Fibrillation, respectively, which are shown below, in that order. Note that all of the subsequent data analysis will be done on the first lead of the ECG signal.

Figure 1: Time series data for healthy control

Figure 2: Time series data for patient with Ventricular Tachycardia

Figure 3: Time series data for patient with Ventricular Flutter

Figure 4: Time series data for patient with Ventricular Fibrillation

We then apply Taken's embedding theorem, using the embedding dimension $d = 3$ and determining ρ , the time delay, using the method of mutual information. Below, we show the embeddings for all of the previous time series from above (in identical order).

Figure 5: Healthy control higher dimensional embedding visual depiction

Figure 6: Ventricular Tachycardia higher dimensional embedding visual depiction

Figure 7: Ventricular Flutter higher dimensional embedding visual depiction

Figure 8: Ventricular Fibrillation higher dimensional embedding visual depiction

Now using the Vietoris Rips Complex and the Rips filtration, we generate the respective persistence diagrams for the above example higher dimensional embeddings.

Figure 9: Healthy Control Persistence Diagram with 0-dimensional and 1-dimensional topological structures

Figure 10: Ventricular Tachycardia Persistence Diagram with 0-dimensional and 1-dimensional topological structures

Figure 11: Ventricular Flutter Persistence Diagram with 0-dimensional and 1-dimensional topological structures

Figure 12: Ventricular Fibrillation Persistence Diagram with 0-dimensional and 1-dimensional topological structures

5. Results and Conclusions

The three main novel steps that we applied to the original time series ECG data was Taken's Embedding with an additional use of Mutual Information with a time delay for added accuracy, along with using these algorithms in conjunction with the Rips Filtration, the Vietoris Rips Complex, and the Scikit Learn Algorithms from the Giotta TDA Library in Python. As can be seen from the persistence diagrams of the healthy and sick patients, one key distinction that can be seen between the healthy controls, tachycardia patients, flutter patients, and fibrillation patients is by comparing the latest death time of their components: the trend is that healthy controls have a latest death time of a 0 dimensional component in the range 0.15-0.20, tachycardia patients have one in the range 0.8-1.0, flutter patients have one in the range 1.5-2.0, and fibrillation patients have one in the range 2.0-2.4.

This conclusion was formed on the basis of hundreds of thousands of sample time series data for each of the four separate cases of patients. The use of the latest death time of the 0-dimensional component is due to its immunity to noise, as it is the point representing a topological component of minimum dimension and furthest from the diagonal line. In addition, the claim that the one-dimensional homology of point clouds is not particularly useful for distinguishing them due to their large dependence on the parameters use in the time series embedding is supported here. There does not appear to be any significant correlation between the one-dimensional topological features of the sick patients or the healthy patients. This is likely due to higher dimensional components being more susceptible to noise in comparison to lower dimensional components.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my mentor Dr. Krassimir Penev for his guidance throughout the research process.

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